

Progressive Failure Analysis for Laminated Composite Plates Under Multiple In-plane Loads

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ABSTRACT

A progressive failure analysis has been developed for predicting failure and response of fiber-reinforced organic matrix composite laminates subjected to in-plane tensile and shear loads. Damage due to matrix and fiber failures and its effect on laminate residual properties were the focus of the study. The model consists of three parts: constitutive modeling, damage growth prediction and stress analysis. A user-friendly nonlinear finite element computer code was developed based on the model. The predictions based on the model agreed very well with existing data.

1. INTRODUCTION

Damage in organic matrix laminated composites can appear at an early loading stage and continue to accumulate inside the materials until the laminates can no longer sustain the applied loads. The presence of damage can degrade the mechanical properties and affect both the response and strength of the composites.

Accordingly, extensive studies have been performed for predicting the progressive failure in laminated composites [1 – 4]. However, the primary concern of majority of these works was matrix cracking failure in cross-ply laminates under a simple loading condition. In practice, laminates with multi-directional layups are used, and the laminates may be subjected to multi-axial loads. None of the existing models can be utilized directly to evaluate the response and failure of a multi-directional laminate under a combined loading condition.

Therefore, a progressive failure analysis was developed for predicting the failure and response of laminated composites subjected to combined in-plane tensile and shear loads [5, 6]. Due to space limitation this paper only briefly summarizes the model.

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2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a composite laminate with or without a cutout and subjected to biaxial tensile and shear loads as shown in Figure 1. It was desired to determine,

1. the response of the laminate to the applied loads;
2. the type and the extent of damage as a function of the applied loads;
3. the failure load of the laminate;

3. PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODEL

The progressive failure analysis model consists of three parts: 1) constitutive modeling, 2) damage growth prediction and 3) stress analysis. The constitutive modeling is to establish the relationship between ply properties and damage of a laminate under consideration. The damage growth prediction is to estimate the state of damage and the mode of failure in the laminate as a function of the applied loads. The stress analysis is to calculate the stresses and strains and the response of the laminate due to the applied loads and to predict the residual stiffness at given loads.

3.1 Constitutive Modeling The development of the ply constitutive equations including the effect of damage was based on the assumption that the composites containing damage could still be treated as a continuous elastic body with degraded material properties. Only the in-plane failure modes, matrix cracking, fiber-matrix shear-out and fiber breakage, that are associated with the tension and shear failures were considered in the analysis. Accordingly, the mechanical properties of each ply in a damaged laminate may vary from ply to ply, depending upon the failure mode and the state of damage in each ply.

For matrix cracking failure, the state of damage was characterized by crack density ϕ . Therefore, an analytical model was developed based on two-dimensional elasticity [3, 5, 6, 7], to determine ply stiffness degradation as a function of crack density. The degraded stiffness of each ply in a laminate may vary from ply to ply depending upon the ply orientation of the laminate and the thickness of each ply in the laminate [5].

However, for fiber-matrix shear-out failure, the damage is associated with the excessive shear deformation along the fiber direction which can lead to catastrophic failure of the laminate. In order to estimate the stiffness degradation due to this type of damage, a model based on the continuum damage mechanics [5, 6] was developed. It was assumed that the degree of material degradation of a ply due to shear-out failure is a function of the cracks accumulated in that ply.

For fiber breakage, a model was developed based on the hypothesis [5, 8] that the stiffness degradation due to fiber breakage was associated with the extent of fiber failure area. Accordingly, by combining the three degradation models, the effective stiffness of the m -th ply in a multi-directional laminate including the effect of three modes of damage can be expressed as follows:

$$[Q^D]_m = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{xx}(\phi) & Q_{xy}(\phi) & 0 \\ Q_{yx}(\phi) & Q_{yy}(\phi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy}(\phi) \end{pmatrix}_m \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_s \end{pmatrix}_m \begin{pmatrix} d_f & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_f \end{pmatrix}_m \quad (1)$$

and

$$d_s = e^{-\left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_0}\right)^\eta} \quad (2)$$

$$d_f = e^{-\left(\frac{A_f}{\delta^2}\right)^\beta} \quad (3)$$

where, ϕ_0 is the saturation crack density of the m -th ply and η is the shape parameter dictating the rate of stiffness degradation due to fiber-matrix shear-out failure. A_f is the extent of the predicted fiber failure area, and δ is the fiber interaction length for a unidirectional composite under consideration. β is a parameter which controls the rate of material degradation due to fiber failure. Also x and y denote coordinates parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction, respectively.

Note that in Equation (1), the first matrix on the right hand side is associated with matrix cracking, the second one is related to fiber-matrix shearing and the third one corresponds to fiber breakage failure.

If the ply shear stress-shear strain nonlinear relationship is also considered in each ply, then, the modified ply constitutive equations has to be used which can be found in [5, 6].

3.2 Damage Growth Criteria In order to use the ply constitutive relation given by Equation 1, the mode of failure and the state of damage in the ply must be known. Therefore, a set of damage growth criteria were developed for predicting the mode of failure and the state of damage in a ply.

Matrix Cracking For matrix cracking, the criterion has the following form [5]:

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{yy}}{Y_t(\phi)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xy}}{S(\phi)}\right)^2 = e_M^2 \quad (4)$$

where, $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$ are the effective transverse tensile and shear stresses in the ply, respectively. Note that when e_M^2 reaches unity, matrix cracking failure corresponding to a crack density is predicted.

Fiber-Matrix Shear-Out The criterion for predicting fiber-matrix shear-out failure can be described as follows [5]:

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xx}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xy}}{S(\phi)}\right)^2 = e_S^2 \quad (5)$$

where, $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$ is the effective ply stress in the fiber direction and X_t is the longitudinal tensile strength of a unidirectional composite. Failure is predicted due to fiber-matrix shear-out when e_S^2 reaches unity.

Fiber Breakage For fiber breakage failure, the failure criterion has the following form [5]:

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xx}}{X_t}\right) = e_F \quad (6)$$

Failure is predicted due to fiber breakage when ϵ_F reaches unity.

$Y_t(\phi)$ and $S(\phi)$ are defined as the effective strengths of a ply, which is the minimum effective stresses required to initiate matrix cracks with a crack density ϕ [5].

If the applied stress field satisfies one of the criteria, then damage is predicted and the mode of failure is identified. Both moduli and strengths of the failed ply have to be modified based on the predicted type and state of damage. The stresses would have to be recalculated and then be applied to the damage growth criteria with the new effective strengths corresponding to a next damage state. The procedure would be repeated until the laminate can no longer sustain any additional load. The final failure load is then predicted.

3.3 Stress Analysis A nonlinear finite element method was developed based on large deformation theory to calculate stresses and deformations of composite laminates under multiple in-plane loads [5]. The constitutive equations and the damage growth criteria were implemented in the analysis.

4. COMPUTER CODE

A user-friendly computer code, designated as "PDCOMP", has been developed based on the study. For a given laminate under in-plane tensile and shear loads, the code can provide the following information:

1. stiffness degradation as a function of the applied loads;
2. the failure mode and the state of damage as a function of the applied loads in each layer;
3. the response of the laminate as a function of the applied loads;

The code can be obtained from F.K. Chang at the address given in the first page.

5. COMPARISONS

5.1 Prediction of Stiffness Reduction Figure 2 presents the comparison between the measured and predicted normalized laminate stiffness as a function of crack density in the 90° ply of a $[0/90/0]_s$, AS4/3502 composite laminate subjected to uniaxial tensile loading. The predictions seemed to agree with the data reasonably well. The test data were taken from [9].

5.2 Prediction of Laminate Strength The strength envelope as a function of the biaxial stresses for $[90/\pm 45/0]_s$, AS4/3501-6 composite laminate was measured by Swanson et al. [10]. Figure 3 shows the comparison between the measured and the predicted strength envelopes. Good correlation between the predictions and the experiments were obtained. Apparently, laminates in a biaxial loading state, can sustain much higher stresses compared to a uniaxial loading state.

The measured and predicted ultimate strength of $[0/90/0/90]_s$, AS4/938 composite laminates with a central slit and subjected to uniaxial tensile loading is shown in Figure 4. The width (W) to diameter (D) ratio was four, for all the comparisons shown in the figure. The test data were taken from [11]. The predictions based on the model agreed very well with the test data for a wide range of panel widths.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A progressive failure model has been developed for predicting failure and response of laminated composites subjected to in-plane tensile and shear loads. The model takes

into account of three in-plane failure modes: matrix cracking, fiber-matrix shear-out and fiber breakage. The predictions from the computer code based on the model compared favorably with the available experimental data.

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Figure 1. Laminated composite plates under a combination of in-plane tensile and shear loads.

Figure 2. Comparison between the measured and the predicted normalized laminate stiffness of a [0/90/0]_s, AS4/3502 composite laminate, subjected to a uniaxial tensile load. Test data were taken from [9]. (1 in = 25.4 mm)

Figure 3. Comparison between the predicted strength and the test data for a [90/±45/0]_s, AS4/3501-6 composite laminate subjected to biaxial tensile loads. The test data were taken from [10]. (1 ksi = 6.895 Mpa)

Figure 4. Comparison between the predicted notch strength and the test data for a $[0/90/0/90]_s$, AS4/938 composite laminate subjected to uniaxial tensile loading. W and $2H$ are the width and total thickness of the laminate, respectively. The test data were taken from [11]. (1 ksi = 6.895 Mpa, 1 inch = 25.4 mm)